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A two-stage approximation strategy for piecewise smooth functions in 2-D and 3-D

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Abstract

Given values of a piecewise smooth function f on a square grid within a domain $[0, 1]^d$, $d = 2, 3$, we look for a piecewise adaptive approximation to f . Standard approximation techniques achieve reduced approximation orders near the boundary of the domain and near curves of jump singularities of the function or its derivatives. The insight used here is that the behavior near the boundaries, or near a singularity curve, is fully characterized and identified by the values of certain differences of the data across the boundary and across the singularity curve. We refer to these values as the signature of f . In this paper, we aim at using these values in order to define the approximation. That is, we look for an approximation whose signature is matched to the signature of f . Given function data on a grid, assuming the function is piecewise smooth, first, the singularity structure of the function is identified. For example in the 2-D case, we find an approximation to the curves separating between smooth segments of f . Secondly, simultaneously we find the approximations to the different segments of f . A system of equations derived from the principle of matching the signature of the approximation and the function with respect to the given grid defines a first stage approximation. A second stage improved approximation is constructed using a global approximation to the error obtained in the first stage approximation.

1 Introduction

Given data values of a piecewise smooth function on a square grid within a domain Ω , one looks for high order approximation to f . Standard approximation techniques achieve

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reduced approximation orders near the boundary of the domain and near curves of jump singularities of the function or its derivatives. In a recent paper [1] the authors suggest a novel idea for treating the univariate case using a corrected subdivision approximation. This paper presents a two-stage approximation algorithm: In the first stage, the data is made smooth by subtracting a proper piecewise polynomial data. In the second stage, a smooth approximation to the smooth data is generated, e.g., by subdivision, and the piecewise polynomial used in the first stage is being added to the smooth approximation to produce the final approximation. Other ways of special treatment near boundaries and close to singularities, also for the univariate case, are reviewed in [1].

The approximation procedure suggested in [1] begins with the construction of Taylor series' type approximations to the jumps of the derivatives of f across the singular point s . This approach is not easily transferred into the multivariate case where the singularities of the function may occur along curves in the 2-D case or across surfaces in the 3-D case. We propose here an alternative way for approaching the 1-D case, a way which is naturally transferable into the multivariate case. Within this approach, we apply a signature operator which is used both for identifying the singularity location and for deriving smooth data to be used in the second approximation stage. The final approximation comprises an efficient approximation to the singularity curve in the 2-D case, or the singularity surface in 3-D, plus high order approximations to the different smooth pieces of f .

Regarding the treatment of singularities, linear algorithms suffer from Gibbs-like oscillations when approximating functions with discontinuities. The algorithms that adapt to discontinuities, use their location or, at least, the location of the intervals that contains them. In the case of having information of the point-values of the function, we are not able to retrieve the position of jump discontinuities. The 1-D algorithms that can be found in the literature produce diffusion in the intervals that contain the discontinuities and the order of accuracy is lost. Our algorithm does not require the exact singularity location, and yet, as proved and as shown by numerical examples it achieves high accuracy approximation in the interval containing the jump discontinuity.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the general framework of our signature-based two-stage approximation strategy for the 1-D case. It presents an analysis of the approximation order both near and far from the discontinuities. In Section 3 we present the application of the same strategy to the 2-D problem of approximating a piecewise smooth function with jump discontinuities across one or more smooth curves. One of the novel components of the algorithm is the efficient approximation of the singularity curves, supported by an approximation analysis and validated by several numerical examples. The 3-D algorithm is presented, analysed and tested in Section 4. The algorithm includes the approximation of the singularity surface, using the same approach as in the 2-D case, namely, approximating the signed-distance function from the unknown singularity surface. An analysis of this approximation is presented. It is also proved that the resulting final approximation does not exhibit the Gibbs phenomenon.

2 The 1-D procedure

In this section, we present the main idea for univariate function approximation. We have chosen to work with spline approximation, but the same idea can be used for

approximation with other basis functions, with similar performance. We describe the fitting strategy using B-spline basis functions and develop the computation algorithm.

2.1 The signature of the data

Let f be a piecewise smooth function on $[0, 1]$, defined by combining two pieces $f_1 \in C^m[0, s]$ and $f_2 \in C^m(s, 1]$.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} f_1(x) & x < s, \\ f_2(x) & x \geq s. \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

We are given function values $\{f_i \equiv f(ih)\}_{i=0}^N$, $h = 1/N$. We artificially extend the data outside $[0, 1]$ with zero values, $\{f_i = 0\}_{i=-k}^{-1}$, $\{f_i = 0\}_{i=N+1}^{N+k}$.

An example is shown in blue in Figure 1. The process of approximation suggested here requires finding the position s of the discontinuity of the function. As described in [4], in case of discontinuity at s , the interval $(jh, (j+1)h)$ containing s can be detected if $h \leq h_c$,

$$h_c := \frac{|[f]|}{4 \sup_{t \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{s\}} |f'(t)|}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $[f]$ is the jump in the function f . In the following we assume that this interval is identified.

We suggest that significant information about the function, and especially its behavior near the boundaries and near the singularity point s is encrypted in the sequence of differences of $\bar{f} = \{f_i\}_{i=-k}^{N+k}$. Consider the vector $\bar{d}^k(\bar{f})$ of forward k th-order differences of \bar{f} , with the elements

$$d_i^k = \Delta^k f_i, \quad i = -k, \dots, N. \quad (2.3)$$

These differences are going to be typically $O(1)$ near $x = 0$ and $x = 1$ and also near s , and for $k \leq m$ they are $O(h^k)$ away from the endpoints and the singular point. Fifth order differences of the data in Figure 1 are shown in Figure 2. Away from the singularity and the endpoints, the values are of magnitude $\sim 10^{-6}$. Clearly, the values of the five-order differences show us the critical points for the approximation of f . Furthermore, they include important information about the function near the critical points.

Definition 2.1. The signature of a function - $\sigma_k(g)$

Let g be a function on $[0, 1]$. We denote by \bar{g} the vector of values of g at the points $\{ih\}_{i=0}^N$, padded by k zero values on each side as above. We refer to the vector of the forward k th-order differences of the data vector \bar{g} as the signature of g , and we denote it as $\sigma_k(g) = \bar{d}^k(\bar{g})$, $\sigma_k(g) \in \mathbb{R}^{N+k}$.

2.2 Constructing the first stage approximation

We choose to build the approximation using m th-order spline functions, represented by the B-spline basis. Let $B_d^{[m]}(x)$ be the B-spline of order m with equidistant knots

Figure 1: An example of a non-smooth function, with zero padding on both sides, together with the B-spline basis functions used to the right and to the left of the singularity.

Figure 2: The signature of f using fifth order differences.

$\{-md, \dots, -2d, -d, 0\}$. $N_d = 1/d + m - 1$ is the number of B-splines whose shifts do not vanish in $[0, 1]$ (we assume N_d is integer). The advantage of using spline functions is twofold:

- The locality of the B-spline basis functions.

- Their approximation power, i.e., if $f \in C^m[a, b]$, there exists a spline $S_d^{[m]}$ such that $\|f - S_d^{[m]}\|_{\infty, [a, b]} \leq Cd^m$.

An example of sixth-order B-splines basis functions used in the numerical example below is shown in Figure 1. The B-splines used to approximate f_1 are shown in green, and the B-splines used to approximate f_2 appear in red.

The approach we suggest here involves finding approximations to f_1 and f_2 simultaneously, using two separate spline approximations:

$$S_1 \equiv S_d^{[m]}|_{[0, s]}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} a_{1i} B_d^{[m]}(x - id)|_{[0, s]} \sim f_1, \quad (2.4)$$

and

$$S_2 \equiv S_d^{[m]}|_{(s, 1]}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} a_{2i} B_d^{[m]}(x - id)|_{(s, 1]} \sim f_2. \quad (2.5)$$

Following the framework presented in [1], we present below a two-stage approximation algorithm: In the first stage, the data is made smooth by subtracting a proper piecewise smooth approximation. In the second stage, a smooth approximation to the smooth data is generated and the piecewise approximation used in the first stage is being added to the smooth approximation to produce the final approximation. In this paper the first stage approximation is a piecewise spline S whose signature, $\sigma_k(S)$, matches the signature of f , $\sigma_k(f)$. We define S by a combination of the above S_1 and S_2 . The piecewise spline S depends upon s and upon the coefficients $\{a_{1i}\}$ of S_1 and the coefficients $\{a_{2i}\}$ of S_2 . After identifying the interval containing s , the matching process finds the spline coefficients by solving the minimization problem,

$$[\{a_{1i}\}_{i=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{2i}\}_{i=1}^{N_d}] = \arg \min \|\sigma_k(f) - \sigma_k(S)\|_2^2. \quad (2.6)$$

We denote by $B_{1i} \equiv B_d^{[m]}(\cdot - id)|_{[0, s]}$ the restriction of $B_d^{[m]}(\cdot - id)$ to the interval $[0, s]$, and by $B_{2i} \equiv B_d^{[m]}(\cdot - id)|_{(s, 1]}$ the restriction of $B_d^{[m]}(\cdot - id)$ to the interval $(s, 1]$. We concatenate these two sequences of basis functions, $\{B_{1i}\}$ and $\{B_{2i}\}$ into one sequence $\{B_i\}_{i=1}^{2N_d}$, and denote their signatures by $\sigma_i = \sigma_k(B_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, 2N_d$. The induced system of linear equations for the splines' coefficients $a = (\{a_{1i}\}_{i=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{2i}\}_{i=1}^{N_d})$ is $Aa = b$ defined as follows:

$$A_{i,j} = \langle \sigma_i, \sigma_j \rangle, \quad 1 \leq i, j \leq 2N_d, \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$b_i = \langle \sigma_i, \sigma(f) \rangle, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2N_d. \quad (2.8)$$

We denote the resulting piecewise spline approximation by S^* .

Remark 2.2. *Due to the locality of the B-splines, some of the functions $\{B_{1i}\}$ and $\{B_{2i}\}$ may be identically 0. It thus seems better to use only the non-zero basis functions. From our experience, since we use the general inverse approach for solving the system of equations, using all the basis functions gives the same solution. As demonstrated in the 2-D procedure below, other approximation spaces such as tensor product polynomials or trigonometric functions may be used, with similar approximation results.*

Remark 2.3. *The above construction can be carried out in the case of several singular points.*

2.2.1 Univariate numerical example

We consider the approximation of the function

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1+(x-1)^2} & x \geq 0.5, \\ \frac{1}{1+(x-1)^2} + (x + 1.5) \cos(4x) & x < 0.5, \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

given its values on a uniform grid with $h = 0.01$. We have used the signature of f defined by fifth-order forward differences of the extended data and computed an approximation using fifth-degree splines with equidistant knots' distance $d = 0.1$. For this case, the matrix A is of size 32×32 , and $\text{rank}(A) = 22$. We have solved the linear system using Matlab general inverse procedure `pinv`, together with an iterative refinement algorithm (described in [10], [8]) to obtain a high precision solution. The results are shown in Figure 3 depicting the approximation error $f - S^*$, showing maximal error $\sim 1.75 \times 10^{-4}$.

Figure 3: The first stage approximation error $f - S^*$.

2.3 First stage approximation order analysis

We begin by deriving an estimate for the approximation of the signature of f by the signature of S^* .

Proposition 2.4. *Let f , S and σ_k be defined as above, and let S^* be the piecewise spline function of order $m \geq k$ minimizing the signature functional*

$$F(S) \equiv \|\sigma_k(f) - \sigma_k(S)\|_2^2.$$

Then,

$$\|\sigma_k(f - S^*)\|_\infty \leq CN^{\frac{1}{2}}h^k. \quad (2.10)$$

Proof. Let us first estimate the minimal value of $F(S) \equiv \|\sigma_k(f) - \sigma_k(S)\|_2^2$. We do it by finding a function \tilde{S} for which $F(\tilde{S})$ is small.

Recalling that S is a piecewise spline function of order $m \geq k$, it follows that both $\sigma_k(f)$ and $\sigma_k(S)$ are $O(h^k)$ away from the boundaries and the singularity, and so is $\sigma_k(f - S)$. Let the knots' distance d be small enough such that the number of B-splines influencing each of the intervals $[0, s]$ and $[s, 1]$ is greater than $2k + 2$. We can find \tilde{S}_1 which coincides with f_1 at $k + 1$ data points at both ends of the interval $[0, s]$, and \tilde{S}_2 which coincides with f_2 at $k + 1$ data points at both ends of the interval $[s, 1]$. The combination \tilde{S} of \tilde{S}_1 and \tilde{S}_2 satisfies $\sigma_k(f - \tilde{S}) = 0$ near 0, near s and near 1. Combining this with the observation that $\sigma(f - \tilde{S}) \leq Ch^k$ away from 0, s and 1, it follows that

$$F(\tilde{S}) = \|\sigma_k(f - \tilde{S})\|_2^2 \leq C^2Nh^{2k}. \quad (2.11)$$

Denoting by S^* the minimizer of $F(S)$,

$$\|\sigma_k(f - S^*)\|_\infty = \|\sigma_k(f) - \sigma_k(S^*)\|_\infty \leq CN^{\frac{1}{2}}h^k. \quad (2.12)$$

□

Proposition 2.5. *Let Σ_k is the matrix representation of the linear operator defining the signature σ_k , and let S^* be the piecewise spline function minimizing $F(S)$. Then,*

$$|f(ih) - S^*(ih)| \leq C\|\Sigma_k^{-1}\|_1N^{\frac{1}{2}}h^k, \quad 0 \leq i \leq N. \quad (2.13)$$

Proof. The result follows directly from the estimate (2.10) for the vector of signatures of $f - S^*$ and the definition of Σ_k . □

It turns out that $\|\Sigma_k^{-1}\|_1 = O(N^{k-1})$ which in view of (2.5) gives us the slow decreasing bound

$$|f(ih) - S^*(ih)| \leq Ch^{0.5}, \quad 0 \leq i \leq N. \quad (2.14)$$

We note that the numerical results reveal much faster convergence rates, as demonstrated by the above numerical example (in Figure 3). In any case, as presented below, we consider S^* as the first stage approximation to f , and the approximation is much improved by the final second stage approximation which is obtained by correcting the first one.

2.4 The corrected approximation

The 1-D procedure developed in [1] is a two-stage procedure. In the first stage, the non-smooth data is transformed into smooth data by subtracting a one-sided polynomial with appropriate jumps in its derivatives. The second stage is a correction step using a standard subdivision process for approximating the residual smooth data. Here again the approximation S^* obtained by matching the signature of f is just the first stage in computing the final approximation to f . The second stage is based upon the observation that the error $e = f - S^*$, evaluated at the data points $\{ih\}_{i=-k}^{N+k}$, forms a ‘smooth’ data sequence, as is clearly observable in Figure 3 for a specific example. Applying an appropriate smooth approximation procedure to the data $\{e(ih)\}_{i=-k}^{N+k}$, we obtain an approximation $\tilde{e}(x)$ to e . The final corrected approximation is defined as

$$\tilde{f} \equiv S^* + \tilde{e}. \quad (2.15)$$

The approximation error $f - \tilde{f}$ is the same as the error $e - \tilde{e}$. To estimate this error we should examine how smooth is e . If f and its derivatives are discontinuous at s , then $e = f - S^*$ would also be discontinuous at s . However, as shown below, the smaller the signature of $e = f - S^*$ is made, the smaller is the jump in e and its derivatives across s .

To build the approximation to e we may use any univariate approximation method. However, it is simpler to understand the approximation error if we use a local approximation method, such as subdivision or quasi-interpolation by splines. We assume that the approximation to e is defined as

$$\tilde{e}(x) = \sum_{i=-k}^{N+k} e(ih)\phi_\ell(x/h - i), \quad (2.16)$$

where ϕ_ℓ is of finite support $[-\ell, \ell]$, and polynomials of degree $\leq \ell$ are reproduced,

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} p(ih)\phi_\ell(x/h - i) = p(x), \quad p \in \Pi_\ell. \quad (2.17)$$

For example, the cubic spline quasi-interpolation basis function is supported on $[-3, 3]$ and is defined as

$$\phi_3(x) = -\frac{1}{6}B_3(x-1) + \frac{4}{3}B_3(x) - \frac{1}{6}B_3(x+1), \quad (2.18)$$

where B_3 is the cubic B-spline with integer knots $\{-2, -1, 0, 1, 2\}$.

Proposition 2.6. *Let S^* be defined by minimizing $F(S)$, \tilde{e} be defined as above with $k \leq \ell < m$, and consider the final approximation $\tilde{f} = S^* + \tilde{e}$ to f . At points which are of distance $\geq \ell h$ from s and from 0 and 1*

$$|f(x) - \tilde{f}(x)| \leq Ch^{\ell+1}, \quad (2.19)$$

and at points near s or near 0 or 1

$$|f(x) - \tilde{f}(x)| \leq Ch^{k-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (2.20)$$

Denoting by $[f^{(j)}]_s$ the jump in the j -th derivative of f across s , $[f^{(j)}]_s = f^{(j)}(s_+) - f^{(j)}(s_-)$, then

$$|[f^{(j)}]_s| - [\tilde{f}^{(j)}]_s| = O(h^{k-j-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad 0 \leq j \leq k-1. \quad (2.21)$$

In particular, it follows that the approximation \tilde{f} does not exhibit the Gibbs phenomenon near s , and the same is also true near 0 and near 1.

Proof. For both cases we use the reconstruction property (2.17) of the quasi-interpolation operator. If $\ell < m$, m being the order of the spline S^* and the smoothness degree of f_1 and f_2 , then at points x which are of distance $\geq \ell h$ from s and from 0 and 1, the reconstruction property implies

$$|e(x) - \tilde{e}(x)| \leq Ch^{\ell+1}, \quad (2.22)$$

which is equivalent to (2.19).

Let us check the approximation power near s , a similar argument holds near 0 and 1. Assuming that $jh \leq s < (j+1)h$, let $p \in \Pi_{k-1}$ interpolate $\{e(ih)\}$, $j-k < i \leq j$, thus

$$e(ih) - p(ih) = 0, \quad j-k < i \leq j. \quad (2.23)$$

Using (2.12) and (2.23) it follows that

$$e(ih) - p(ih) = O(h^{k-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad j \leq i \leq j+\ell. \quad (2.24)$$

Therefore, by the locality of ϕ_ℓ , $\tilde{e} - p$ are $O(h^{k-\frac{1}{2}})$ near s . Using the reproduction property (2.17), taking into account the finite support of ϕ_ℓ , it follows that

$$|e(x) - \tilde{e}(x)| \leq Ch^{k-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (2.25)$$

which implies the required result (2.20).

To check the approximation to the jumps in the derivatives across s , it is enough to check the jumps in $e = f - S^*$. We follow here the approach used in [1], namely, estimating the derivatives of the functions from both sides of s using one-sided local polynomial approximations. By (2.23) the above polynomial p interpolates $e(x)$ at k data points to the left of s . Let $q \in \Pi_{k-1}$ be the polynomial interpolating $e(x)$ at k data points to the right of s . By (2.24) q is an $O(h^{k-\frac{1}{2}})$ perturbation of p . Hence, it follows that

$$|q^{(j)}(s_+) - p^{(j)}(s_-)| = O(h^{k-j-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad 0 \leq j \leq k-1,$$

which implies

$$|[e^{(j)}]_s| = O(h^{k-j-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad 0 \leq j \leq k-1.$$

□

2.4.1 Back to the numerical example - The corrected approximation

Coming back to the numerical example in Section 2.2.1, we compute the corrected approximation by applying cubic spline interpolation to the smoothed data and adding

S^* to it. While the maximal error in the first stage approximation S^* is $\sim 1.75 \times 10^{-4}$, the maximal error in the corrected approximation is $\sim 1.7 \times 10^{-9}$, as it can be observed in Figure 4.

Comparing the performance of the above 1-D procedure to existing algorithms, we note that the algorithms presented in [1] and [2] produce comparable high precision approximations. Furthermore, this algorithm in [1] is simpler to apply, and like the above algorithm, it gives an approximation without Gibbs oscillations and without diffusion near the point of the jump discontinuity. The main objective of suggesting the above two-stage signature-based algorithm is to present a new framework that can be used for deriving efficient approximations for the 2-D and the 3-D problems, as demonstrated in the coming sections.

Figure 4: The corrected approximation error $f - \tilde{f}$.

3 The 2-D procedure

Let f be a piecewise smooth function on $[0, 1]^2$, defined by the combination of two pieces $f_1 \in C^m[\Omega_1]$ and $f_2 \in C^m[\Omega_2]$, $\Omega_2 = [0, 1]^2 \setminus \Omega_1$. We assume that we are given function values $\{f_{ij} \equiv f(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$, $h = 1/N$. Artificially we extend the data outside $[0, 1]^2$ with zero values, $\{f_{ij} = 0\}_{i=-k}^{-1}$, $\{f_{ij} = 0\}_{i=N+1}^{N+k}$, $\{f_{ij} = 0\}_{j=-k}^{-1}$, $\{f_{ij} = 0\}_{j=N+1}^{N+k}$. We do not know the position of the dividing curve separating Ω_1 and Ω_2 . We denote this curve by Γ , and we assume that it is a smooth curve. As in the 1-D case, the existence of a singularity curve in $[0, 1]^2$ significantly influences standard approximation procedures,

especially near Γ , and the approximation power also deteriorates near the boundaries. As in the univariate case, the approximation procedure described below is based upon matching a signature of the function and the approximant. The computation algorithm involves finding approximations to f_1 and f_2 simultaneously, followed by a correction step. The first stage is the approximation of Γ .

3.1 Approximating the singularity curve Γ

Finding a good approximation of the singularity curve Γ is more involved than finding the singularity point s in the univariate case. To simplify the presentation we assume that Ω_1 and Ω_2 are simply connected domains and the set of data points $P = \{(ih, jh) \mid 0 \leq i, j \leq N\}$ is consequently divided into two sets:

$$\begin{cases} P_1 = \{(ih, jh) \in \Omega_1, 0 \leq i, j \leq N\}, \\ P_2 = \{(ih, jh) \in \Omega_2, 0 \leq i, j \leq N\}. \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

As in the univariate case, we assume that h is small enough to assure the detection of the singularity interval along each horizontal and vertical line in $[0, 1]^2$. This involves estimating a critical h_c as in (2.2) along horizontal and vertical lines (as in [4]). For each $0 \leq j \leq N$ consider the data values along the horizontal line $y = jh$, $\{f_{ij}\}_{i=0}^N$. As in the univariate case, we find the interval containing the singularity, if exists, and denote the midpoint of this interval as s_j . The points $\{(s_j, jh)\}$ found are at distance $< h/2$ from Γ . Similarly, we find points along the vertical lines $\{(ih, t_i)\}$ which are near Γ . An important outcome of this process is that it identifies and separates data points from both sides of the singularity curve. Another way of achieving this is suggested in [3].

Let us continue the description of the procedure alongside the following numerical example:

Consider the piecewise smooth function on $[0, 1]^2$ with a jump singularity across the curve Γ which is the quarter circle defined by $(x+1)^4 + (y+1)^4 = 10$. The test function is shown in Figure 5 and is defined as

$$f(x, y) = \begin{cases} (x + y + 2) \cos(4x) + \sin(4(x + y)), & (x + 1)^4 + (y + 1)^4 \geq 10, \\ \sin(4(x + y)), & (x + 1)^4 + (y + 1)^4 < 10. \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

Let us denote by Q_0 all the points $\{(s_j, jh)\}$ and $\{(ih, t_i)\}$ found as described above for $h = 0.025$. We display the points Q_0 (in red) in Figure 6, on top of the curve Γ (in green). Now we use these points to construct a tensor product cubic spline $T(x, y)$, whose zero level curve defines the approximation to Γ . To construct T we first overlay on $[0, 1]^2$ a net of $n \times n$ points, Q , $Q \subset P$. These are the green points displayed in Figure 7, for $n = 9$.

To each point in Q we assign the value of its distance from the set Q_0 , with a plus sign for the points which are in P_1 , and a minus sign for the points in P_2 . To each point in Q_0 we assign the value zero. The spline function T is now defined by the least-squares approximation to the values at all the points $Q \cup Q_0$. We have used here tensor product cubic spline on a uniform mesh with knots' distance $d = 0.25$. It can be shown that the

Figure 5: The test function for the 2-D non-smooth case.

Figure 6: The singularity curve Γ (green) and the points Q_0 .

corresponding normal equations are non-singular if $d > 1/n$. We denote the zero level curve of the resulting T as $\tilde{\Gamma}$, and this curve is depicted in yellow in Figure 7. It seems

Figure 7: The approximation of the singularity curve Γ (yellow).

that $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is already a good approximation to Γ (in green), and yet it may not separate completely the points P_1 from the points P_2 .

3.1.1 Curve approximation analysis

A similar approximation quality $\tilde{\Gamma} \sim \Gamma$ is obtained if we define the spline \tilde{D} by quasi-interpolation to the signed-distance values defined on Q . In the following proposition, we analyze the quality of the approximation $\tilde{\Gamma} \sim \Gamma$, obtained by quasi-interpolation, for a restricted class of singularity curves. The result is also applicable to the 3-D example in Section 4.

Proposition 3.1. *Assume Γ is a C^4 smooth curve in $[0, 1]^2$ with minimal curvature radius $> R$, and such that its R -neighborhood is not self-intersecting and not intersecting the boundaries of $[0, 1]^2$. Let Q be a mesh of $n \times n$ points in $[0, 1]^2$, of mesh size $\delta < R/10$. Let Γ subdivide $[0, 1]^2$ into two domains Ω_1 and Ω_2 , and separate the mesh points Q into Q_1 and Q_2 respectively. Let us attach signed-distance values to the mesh points Q as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned} D(p) &= \text{dist}(p, \Gamma), & p \in Q_1, \\ D(p) &= -\text{dist}(p, \Gamma), & p \in Q_2. \end{aligned}$$

Let A be the quasi-interpolation operator from sets of values on Q to the space of bi-cubic splines on $[0, 1]^2$ with uniform mesh of mesh size δ , and assume $\|A\|_\infty < \beta$. Let T_ϵ be the bi-cubic spline defined by applying A to the perturbed signed-distance data

$$\tilde{D}(p) = D(p) + \epsilon_p, \quad |\epsilon_p| \leq \epsilon,$$

and let Γ_ϵ be the zero-level curve of T_ϵ . Then

$$\text{dist}(\Gamma, \Gamma_\epsilon) \leq C_0\delta^4 + \beta\epsilon. \quad (3.3)$$

Proof. The exact signed-distance function with respect to Γ is C^4 in an R -neighborhood of Γ . The bi-cubic quasi-interpolation approximation is a compact support operator which reproduces cubic polynomials. It is of the form

$$A(g)(q) = \sum_{p \in M} g(p)\Phi_3(q/\delta - p), \quad q \in [2\delta, 1 - 2\delta]^2, \quad (3.4)$$

where Φ_3 is the bi-cubic spline quasi-interpolation basis function supported on $[-3, 3]^2$, $\Phi_3(x, y) = \phi_3(x)\phi_3(y)$, ϕ_3 defined in (2.18). We denote by D the signed-distance function with respect to Γ , and by N_r the r -neighborhood of Γ . Considering the approximation $A(D)$ of D in $N_{R-3\delta}$

$$A(D)(q) = \sum_{p \in M} D(p)\Phi_3(q/\delta - p) \equiv T_0(q), \quad q \in N_{R-3\delta}, \quad (3.5)$$

it follows from the approximation properties of A that

$$|D(q) - T_0(q)| \leq C_0\delta^4, \quad q \in N_{R-3\delta}. \quad (3.6)$$

Furthermore, the gradient of T_0 approximates the gradient of D in $N_{R-3\delta}$:

$$\|\nabla D(q) - \nabla T_0(q)\| \leq C_1\delta^3, \quad q \in N_{R-3\delta}. \quad (3.7)$$

Since $\|\nabla D(q)\| = 1$, for a small enough δ it follows that $\|\nabla T_0(q)\|$ is also close to 1.

Using $\|A\|_\infty < \beta$, it follows that

$$|T_0(q) - T_\epsilon(q)| < \beta\epsilon, \quad q \in [2\delta, 1 - 2\delta]^2, \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$T_\epsilon(q) = \sum_{p \in M} \tilde{D}(p)B(q - p), \quad q \in [2\delta, 1 - 2\delta]^2. \quad (3.9)$$

Using (3.6) and (3.8) it follows that

$$|D(q) - T_\epsilon(q)| < C_0\delta^4 + \beta\epsilon, \quad q \in N_{R-3\delta}. \quad (3.10)$$

Consider now the two curves $\Gamma_1 \subset \Omega_1$ and $\Gamma_2 \subset \Omega_2$ which are at distance $\beta\epsilon + C_0\delta^4$ from Γ . For small enough ϵ and δ both curves are in $N_{R-3\delta}$. By definition $D(q) = \beta\epsilon + C_0\delta^4$ for $q \in \Gamma_1$ and $D(q) = -(\beta\epsilon + C_0\delta^4)$ for $q \in \Gamma_2$. Hence, using (3.10), it follows that $T_\epsilon(q) > 0$ for $q \in \Gamma_1$ and $T_\epsilon(q) < 0$ for $q \in \Gamma_2$. Since T_ϵ is a continuous function its zero-level curve Γ_ϵ must be between Γ_1 and Γ_2 , implying the result (3.3). To verify that there is only one level-zero curve of T_ϵ we may examine the behaviour of T_ϵ along normals to Γ , using the observation that, for a small enough ϵ , the derivative of T_ϵ along such normal is non-vanishing. □

Corollary 3.2. *Let the singularity curve Γ satisfy the assumptions in Proposition 3.1 and let the approximate signed-distance values be defined as*

$$\tilde{D}(p) = \text{dist}(p, Q_0), \quad p \in Q_1,$$

$$\tilde{D}(p) = -\text{dist}(p, Q_0), \quad p \in Q_2,$$

where Q_0 is defined above for data spacing h . Using the quasi-interpolation approximation operator A defined in Proposition 3.1, and denoting the resulting approximated curve by $\Gamma_{\delta,h}$,

$$\text{dist}(\Gamma, \Gamma_{\delta,h}) \leq C_0 \delta^4 + 0.6h. \quad (3.11)$$

Proof. By the construction of Q_0 it follows that

$$|D(p) - \tilde{D}(p)| \leq 0.5h.$$

It can also be verified that $\|A\|_\infty < \beta = 1.2$, and the result follows by (3.3). □

Remark 3.3. *In case of a singularity curve intersecting the boundary of $[0, 1]^2$, as in the above example with Γ defined by $(x+1)^4 + (y+1)^4 = 10$, the approximation of Γ using a quasi-interpolation approximation operator exhibits larger errors near the boundary. Better approximation near the boundary, as depicted in Figure 7, is achieved by defining the spline approximation to the signed-distance function by a least-squares procedure as described above. In view of the proof of Proposition 3.1, the analysis of the least-squares approach requires an estimation of the approximation order of the least-squares bicubic spline operator and of its norm, both are non-trivial. We note that univariate least-squares spline approximations are analyzed by deBoor in [5], and are shown to produce full approximation order, e.g., fourth-order for cubic splines. Also, numerically checking the least-squares spline approximation operator used for the above numerical example we have found that its norm is bounded by 1.4. Therefore we conjecture that the result in Proposition 3.1 also applies to the approximation of more general smooth singularity curves using the least-squares approach.*

3.2 Constructing the first stage approximation

As in the univariate case, the approximation strategy is based upon matching some signature of the approximation to the signature of the given function data. One way of defining the signature in the multivariate case is by using univariate difference operators in different directions, and we use this option in the 3-D case in Section 4. For the 2-D case below we define the signature using a multivariate difference operator.

Definition 3.4. The signature of a function - $\sigma(g)$

Let g be a function on $[0, 1]^2$. We denote by \bar{g} the matrix of values of g at the points $\{ih, jh\}_{i=0}^N$, padded by two layers of zero values on each side as above. We define the signature of g as the matrix of discrete biharmonic operator applied to g , namely,

$$\sigma(g) = \Delta_h^2(\bar{g}). \tag{3.12}$$

Considering the test function (3.2), discretized using a mesh size $h = 0.01$, padded by ten layers of zero values all around, its signature is displayed in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8: The signature $\sigma(f)$ of the test function (3.2).

The first stage of the approximation process is similar to the construction in the univariate case defined by equations (2.4), (2.5), (2.6). We look here for an approximation S to f which is a combination of two bivariate splines components:

$$S_1(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{1ij} B_{ij}(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \tilde{\Omega}_1, \tag{3.13}$$

$$S_2(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{2ij} B_{ij}(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \tilde{\Omega}_2, \quad (3.14)$$

where

$$B_{ij}(x, y) = B_d^{[m]}(x - id) B_d^{[m]}(y - jd), \quad (3.15)$$

and

$$\tilde{\Omega}_1 = \{(x, y) \mid T(x, y) \geq 0, (x, y) \in [0, 1]^2\}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$\tilde{\Omega}_2 = \{(x, y) \mid T(x, y) < 0, (x, y) \in [0, 1]^2\}. \quad (3.17)$$

Definition 3.5. The signature of S - $\sigma(S)$

We denote by \bar{S} the matrix of values

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{1ij} B_{ij}(x, y), & (x, y) \in P_1, \\ \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{2ij} B_{ij}(x, y), & (x, y) \in P_2. \end{cases} \quad (3.18)$$

padding by two layers of zero values on each side as above. The signature of S is $\sigma(S) = \Delta_h^2(\bar{S})$.

Having defined the signature of f and of S , we now look for an approximation S such that the signatures of f and S are matched in the least-squares sense:

$$[\{a_{1ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{2ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}] = \arg \min \|\sigma(f) - \sigma(S)\|_2^2. \quad (3.19)$$

3.2.1 The induced system of equations

Definition 3.6. The signature of the B-splines.

For $0 \leq i, j \leq N_d$ let \bar{B}_{1ij} the matrix of $N \times N$ values

$$\begin{cases} B_{ij}(x, y), & (x, y) \in P_1, \\ 0, & (x, y) \in P_2, \end{cases} \quad (3.20)$$

padding by zeros. The signature of \bar{B}_{1ij} , $\sigma(\bar{B}_{1ij})$ include the matrix of Δ_h^2 values of B_{ij} on P_1 . Similarly we define $\sigma(\bar{B}_{2ij})$ using the values of B_{ij} on P_2 :

$$\begin{cases} B_{ij}(x, y), & (x, y) \in P_2, \\ 0, & (x, y) \in P_1. \end{cases} \quad (3.21)$$

We rearrange the signatures $\{\sigma(\bar{B}_{1ij})\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}, \{\sigma(\bar{B}_{2ij})\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}$ as a vector $\sigma(\bar{B})$ of length $2N_d^2$ of signatures.

Rearranging the unknowns $\{a_{1ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{2ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}$ as a vector a of length $2N_d^2$, and rearranging each signature as a vector of length N^2 , the linear system of normal equations for the spline coefficients is $Aa = b$, where

$$A_{k,\ell} = \langle \sigma(\bar{B})_k, \sigma(\bar{B})_\ell \rangle, \quad 1 \leq k, \ell \leq 2N_d^2, \quad (3.22)$$

and

$$b_k = \langle \sigma(\bar{B})_k, \sigma(f) \rangle, \quad 1 \leq k \leq 2N_d^2. \quad (3.23)$$

The above framework is applied to the numerical example with the test function (3.2), with $h = 0.01$ and sixth-order tensor product splines with knots distance $d = 0.1$. Solving the above linear system of equations for the spline coefficients gives us the first stage approximation S^* , combined of two segments, S_1^* on $\tilde{\Omega}_1$ and S_2^* on $\tilde{\Omega}_2$.

In Figure 9 we show the error $e = f - S^*$ at the grid points. We observe that e is quite smooth, which means that the piecewise spline approximation S^* has captured well the singularity structure of f , both across Γ and along the boundaries.

Figure 9: The error in the first stage approximation (9).

3.3 Second stage - corrected approximation

After computing the first stage approximation S^* obtained by matching the signature of f , the second stage is based upon the observation that the error $e = f - S^*$, evaluated at the data points $\{(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$, forms a ‘smooth’ data sequence. Applying an appropriate smooth approximation procedure to the data $\{e(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$, we obtain an approximation $\tilde{e}(x)$ to e . The final corrected approximation is defined as

$$\tilde{f} \equiv S^* + \tilde{e}. \quad (3.24)$$

Continuing the above numerical example, we have applied fifth-order tensor product spline interpolation to e . Figure 10 depicts the values of the error in the final corrected approximation \tilde{f} , evaluated on a fine grid. We observe that the absolute value of the maximal error is 2.8×10^{-7} , and it is attained at the boundary. There are also errors of magnitude $\sim 10^{-8}$ near the singularity curve, but everywhere else the errors are of magnitude $\sim 10^{-10}$. We recall that f is piecewise-defined on Ω_1 and Ω_2 , while S^* is piecewise-defined on $\tilde{\Omega}_1$ and $\tilde{\Omega}_2$. In comparing f and \tilde{f} , we let S^* be piecewise-defined on Ω_1 and Ω_2 , with the same S_1^* and S_2^* . Similar results are obtained if we let f be piecewise-defined on $\tilde{\Omega}_1$ and $\tilde{\Omega}_2$, with the same f_1 and f_2 .

Figure 10: The error in the second stage corrected approximation $f - \tilde{f}$.

3.4 Second numerical example - Two singularity curves

Consider the case of two disjoint singularity curves, subdividing the domain into three sub-domains, $\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \Omega_3$, separated by two smooth curves Γ_1 and Γ_2 , and a piecewise-defined function as in Figure 11.

Function values are given on a uniform grid with $h = 0.01$. In Figure 12 we display the extended data, padded with zeros around the square.

Figure 11: The test function for Example 3.4.

Figure 12: The test function for Example 3.4.

3.4.1 Approximating the singularity curves

As in the first example, we assume that h is small enough to assure the detection of the singularity interval along each horizontal and vertical line in $[0, 1]^2$ ([4]). For each horizontal line $y = jh$ and each vertical line $x = ih$ we detect the intervals containing a singular point, and collect all the midpoints of these intervals, denoting this set of points as Q_0 . Within the detection algorithm we also include a proper ordering algorithm by

which we obtain a subdivision of the set of data points $P = \{(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$ into three disjoint sets, $P_k \in \Omega_k$, $k = 1, 2, 3$. P_1 denotes the set which has neighbors in the two other sets, to be denoted as P_2 and P_3 .

As in the case of one singularity curve, we construct a tensor product cubic spline $T(x, y)$, whose zero level curves approximate Γ_1 and Γ_2 . To construct T we overlay on $[0, 1]^2$ a net of 11×11 points, Q , $Q \subset P$. To each point in Q we assign the value of its

Figure 13: The points $Q \cup Q_0$ used for approximating the singularity curves.

distance from the set Q_0 , with a plus sign for the points which are in P_1 , and for the points in P_2 or P_3 . To each point in Q_0 we assign the value zero. The spline function D is now defined by the least-squares approximation to the values at all the points $Q \cup Q_0$ displayed in Figure 13. We have used here tensor product cubic spline on a uniform mesh with knots' distance $d = 0.2$. We denote the zero level curves of the resulting T as $\tilde{\Gamma}_1, \tilde{\Gamma}_2$, and these curves are depicted in yellow in Figure 14. These curves provide a good approximation to Γ_1 and Γ_2 . To improve the approximation quality we assign higher weight ($\times 100$) to the points Q_0 in the least-squares cost function defining T .

Considering the test function defined in Figure 11, discretized using mesh size $h = 0.01$ padded by ten layers of zero values all around, its Δ_h^2 signature is displayed in Figure 15 below.

For the first stage approximation process we look here for an approximation S to f which is a combination of three bivariate splines components:

$$S_1(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{1ij} B_{ij}(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \tilde{\Omega}_1, \quad (3.25)$$

$$S_2(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{2ij} B_{ij}(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \tilde{\Omega}_2, \quad (3.26)$$

Figure 14: The singularity curves for Example 3.4, in blue, and their approximations, in yellow.

Figure 15: The signature $\sigma(f)$ of the test function with two singularity curves.

$$S_3(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{j=1}^{N_d} a_{3ij} B_{ij}(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \tilde{\Omega}_3, \quad (3.27)$$

where $\tilde{\Omega}_1, \tilde{\Omega}_2, \tilde{\Omega}_3$ are the three disjoint domains defined by the bicubic spline D .

Definition 3.7. The signature of S , $\sigma(S)$: As in Definition 3.5 above, we define \bar{S} as the matrix of values of S at the grid points, padded by two layers of zero values all around, and compute its signature $\sigma(S) = \Delta_h^2(\bar{S})$.

Having defined the signature of f and of S , we now look for an approximation S such that the signatures of f and S are matched in the least-squares sense:

$$[\{a_{1ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{2ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}, \{a_{3ij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}] = \arg \min \|\sigma(f) - \sigma(S)\|_2^2. \quad (3.28)$$

3.4.2 The induced system of equations

For $r = 1, 2, 3$, the signature $\sigma(\bar{B}_{rij})$ include the matrix of Δ_h^2 values of B_{ij} restricted to P_r . We rearrange the signatures $\{\sigma(\bar{B}_{rij})\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}$, $r = 1, 2, 3$, as a vector $\sigma(\bar{B})$ of length $3N_d^2$ of signatures.

Rearranging the unknowns $\{a_{rij}\}_{i,j=1}^{N_d}$, $r = 1, 2, 3$, as a vector a of length $3N_d^2$, the linear system of normal equations for the spline coefficients is $Aa = b$, where

$$A_{k,\ell} = \langle \sigma(\bar{B})_k, \sigma(\bar{B})_\ell \rangle, \quad 1 \leq k, \ell \leq 3N_d^2, \quad (3.29)$$

and

$$b_k = \langle \sigma(\bar{B})_k, \sigma(f) \rangle, \quad 1 \leq k \leq 3N_d^2. \quad (3.30)$$

The above framework is applied to the numerical example with the test function defined in Figure 11, with $h = 0.01$ and sixth-order tensor product splines with knots distance $d = 0.1$. Solving the above linear system of equations for the spline coefficients gives us the first stage approximation S^* , combined of two segments, S_1^* on $\tilde{\Omega}_1$, S_2^* on $\tilde{\Omega}_2$ and S_3^* on $\tilde{\Omega}_3$.

In Figure 16 we show the error $e = f - S^*$ at the initial grid points. We observe that e is quite smooth, which means that the piecewise spline approximation S^* has captured well the singularity structure of f , both across the singularity curves and along the boundaries.

3.5 Second stage - corrected approximation

Here also the error $e = f - S^*$, evaluated at the data points $\{(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$, forms a ‘smooth’ data sequence, and we apply smooth approximation procedure to the data $\{e(ih, jh)\}_{i,j=0}^N$ to obtain an approximation $\tilde{e}(x)$. The final corrected approximation is defined as

$$\tilde{f} \equiv S^* + \tilde{e}. \quad (3.31)$$

Computing \tilde{e} using a fifth order tensor product spline interpolation to e , we derive the final corrected approximation to f , shown in Figure 17.

Figure 18 depicts the values of the error in the final corrected approximation \tilde{f} , evaluated on a fine grid. We observe that the absolute value of the maximal error is 2×10^{-7} , and it is attained at a singularity curve. There are also errors of magnitude $\sim 10^{-8}$ near the boundaries, but everywhere else the errors are of magnitude $\sim 10^{-12}$.

Figure 16: The error in the first stage approximation to f .

4 The 3-D case

Let f be a piecewise smooth function on $[0, 1]^3$, defined by the combination of two pieces $f_1 \in C^m[\Omega_1]$ and $f_2 \in C^m[\Omega_2]$, $\Omega_2 = [0, 1]^3 \setminus \Omega_1$. We assume that we are given function values $\{f_{ijk} \equiv f(ih, jh, kh)\}_{i,j,k=0}^N$, $h = 1/N$. The position of the dividing surface separating Ω_1 and Ω_2 is not given, and one of the challenges is to find a good approximation to this surface. We denote this surface by Θ , and we assume it is a smooth surface. As in the 1-D case, the existence of a singularity in $[0, 1]^3$ significantly influences standard approximation procedures, especially near Θ , and the approximation power also deteriorates near the boundaries. As in the univariate case, the approximation procedure described below is based upon matching a signature of the function and the approximant. The computation algorithm involves finding approximations to f_1 and f_2 simultaneously, followed by a correction step.

The first step of approximating Θ is a straightforward extension of the 2-D procedure for approximating singularity curves.

Consider the piecewise smooth function $f(x, y)$ on $\Omega = [0, 1]^3$ with a jump singularity across the surface Θ which is the surface of the closed 4-ball B of radius 0.33 centered at $(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$,

$$B = \{(x, y, z) \mid (x - 0.5)^4 + (y - 0.5)^4 + (z - 0.5)^4 \leq 0.33^4\},$$

Figure 17: The final corrected approximation to f .

$$f(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} (\exp((x+y)/2) - 1) \sin(2x), & (x, y, z) \notin B, \\ \sin(4(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)) \sin(2(x-y)), & (x, y, z) \in B. \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

Assume we are given function values $\{f_{ijk} = f(ih, jh, kh), (ih, jh, kh) \in \Omega\}$, $h = 1/N$, and artificially extend the data with zero values at m layers around Ω . A cross-section of the extended data of the test function (4.1), for $z = 0.5$, $N = 41$, is shown in Figure 19.

Let us denote by Q_0 all the points $\{(s_{j,k}, jh, kh)\}$, $\{(ih, t_{i,k}, kh)\}$, and $\{(ih, jh, r_{i,j})\}$ found as described above for the 2-D case, i.e., the midpoints of intervals containing a singularity along lines parallel to the axes. We use these points to construct a tensor product cubic spline $T(x, y, z)$, whose zero level surface defines the approximation to Θ . To construct T we first overlay on $[0, 1]^3$ a net of n^3 points, Q . These are the red points displayed in Figure 20, for $n = 11$, together with the points Q_0 , for $h = 0.025$, in blue.

To each point in Q we assign the value of its distance from the set Q_0 , with a plus sign for the points which are in B , and a minus sign for the points outside B . To each point in Q_0 we assign the value zero. The spline function T is now defined by the least-squares approximation to the values at all the points $Q \cup Q_0$. We have used here tensor product cubic spline on a uniform mesh with knots' distance $d = 0.2$. We denote the zero level surface of the resulting T as $\tilde{\Theta}$, and cross-section curves of this surface are depicted in yellow in Figure 21, together with the exact relevant curves of Θ in blue.

Next, we show here some numerical results of the first approximation step and the

Figure 18: The final corrected approximation errors.

correction step for a specific numerical example. Two new ingredients we choose to present here: Using a different signature operator, and using Chebyshev polynomials instead of B-splines for building the first stage approximation. As in the 1-D and the 2-D cases, we artificially extend the data outside $[0, 1]^3$ with zero values.

Here we have used the signature of f defined by r -order forward differences of the extended data in three directions:

$$\sigma_r(f)_{ijk} = [(\Delta_x^r f_{ijk})^2 + (\Delta_y^r f_{ijk})^2 + (\Delta_z^r f_{ijk})^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (4.2)$$

For the numerical example below we use $r = 4$. The first stage approximation is computed by matching the signature of f and the signature of the approximant S defined by two sets of tensor product Chebyshev polynomials, one for the approximation over Ω_1 , and the other for approximation over $\Omega_2 = [0, 1]^3 \setminus \Omega_1$. In 3-D numerical tests, we are limited by the memory constraints of Matlab. We took $h = 0.025$ and tensor product polynomials of degree 8. The error in the resulting approximation is displayed in Figure 22.

Figure 19: A cross-section of the 3-D test function.

Figure 20: The points Q (red) and the points Q_0 (blue).

4.1 3-D analysis

Figure 21: Cross-sections of the approximation of the singularity surface Θ (yellow), at $z = 0.25$ and $z = 0.5$.

Figure 22: First stage approximation error, at $z = 0.5$.

For the 3-D case, we present below the error estimates for the approximation of

the singularity surface. The smoothness of the error in the first stage approximation follows by relevant signature estimates, and the same estimates are used to derive some quantitative conclusions about the jumps of the final approximation and its derivatives across the singularity surface.

Proposition 4.1. *Assume Θ is a C^4 smooth surface in $[0, 1]^3$ with minimal Gauss curvature radius $> R$, and such that its R -neighborhood is not self-intersecting and not intersecting the boundaries of $[0, 1]^3$. Let Q be a mesh of n^3 points in $[0, 1]^3$, of mesh size $\delta < R/10$. Let Θ subdivide $[0, 1]^3$ into two domains Θ_1 and Θ_2 , and separate the mesh points Q into Q_1 and Q_2 respectively. Let us attach signed-distance values to the mesh points Q as follows:*

$$D(p) = \text{dist}(p, \Theta), \quad p \in Q_1,$$

$$D(p) = -\text{dist}(p, \Theta), \quad p \in Q_2.$$

Let A be the quasi-interpolation operator from sets of values on Q to the space of tri-cubic splines on $[0, 1]^3$ with uniform mesh of mesh size δ , and assume $\|A\|_\infty < \beta$. Let T_ϵ the tri-cubic spline defined by applying A to the perturbed signed-distance data

$$\tilde{D}(p) = D(p) + \epsilon_p, \quad |\epsilon_p| \leq \epsilon,$$

and let Θ_ϵ be the zero-level surface of T_ϵ . Then

$$\text{dist}(\Theta, \Theta_\epsilon) \leq C_0 \delta^4 + \beta \epsilon. \quad (4.3)$$

The proof is the same as the proof for the 2-D Proposition 3.1. The tri-cubic quasi-interpolation approximation is a compact support operator which reproduces cubic polynomials of the form

$$A(g)(q) = \sum_{p \in M} g(p) \Phi_3(q/\delta - p), \quad q \in [2\delta, 1 - 2\delta]^3, \quad (4.4)$$

where Φ_3 is the tri-cubic spline quasi-interpolation basis function supported on $[-3, 3]^3$, $\Phi_3(x, y) = \phi_3(x)\phi_3(y)\phi_3(z)$, ϕ_3 defined in (2.18). By the above construction of $\tilde{\Theta}$ it follows, as in the 2-D case, that $\epsilon \leq 0.5h$. It can also be verified that $\beta < 1.33$.

Proposition 4.2. *Let the signature σ_r of the function data be defined by its r th order differences along the 3 axes (4.2). Define S^* by the piecewise n th order tensor product polynomial approximation minimizing $F(S) = \|\sigma_r(f - S)\|_2^2$. Denote by ϵ_n the bound on the errors of the best approximations of f_1 and f_2 by n th order tensor product polynomial. Then*

$$\|\sigma_r(f - S^*)\|_\infty \leq C_1 h^{r-\frac{3}{2}} + C_2 h^{-1} \epsilon_n \equiv \delta_{h,n}. \quad (4.5)$$

Proof. The proof is by an adaptation of the proof of the corresponding 1-D result in Proposition 2.4. Here we have $O(N^3)$ terms in $F(S)$ which are $O(h^{2r})$, representing points which are not near the boundary of Θ or near the boundaries. Near the singularity surface and the boundaries we have $O(N^2)$ terms which are $O(\epsilon_n^2)$. \square

The analysis is simpler if instead of approximating by Chebyshev polynomials we define S^* by m -th order tensor product splines. Using splines with knots' distance $1/n$ it turns out that the approximation bound ϵ_n above can be replaced by Cn^{-m} . Hence, the bound $\delta_{h,n}$ becomes

$$\delta_{h,n} = C_1 h^{r-\frac{3}{2}} + C_2 h^{-1} n^{-m}.$$

If $\delta_{h,n}$ in (4.5) is small, it follows that the error $e = f - S^*$, evaluated at the data points $\{(ih, jh, kh)\}_{i,j,k=0}^N$, forms a 'smooth' data sequence, and we can apply a smooth approximation procedure to the data $\{e(ih, jh, kh)\}_{i,j,k=0}^N$ to obtain an approximation $\tilde{e}(x)$. The final corrected approximation is defined as

$$\tilde{f} \equiv S^* + \tilde{e}. \quad (4.6)$$

Continuing the above numerical example, computing \tilde{e} using cubic tensor product spline interpolation to e , we derive the final corrected approximation to f , shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: The final corrected approximation on a fine mesh, at $z = 0.5$.

Figure 24 depicts the values of the error in the final corrected approximation \tilde{f} , evaluated on a fine grid. We observe that the absolute value of the maximal error is 6.5×10^{-6} , and it is attained at a singularity surface. There are also errors of magnitude $\sim 5 \times 10^{-8}$ near the boundaries, and everywhere else the errors are of magnitude $\sim 10^{-9}$.

The following results implies that if $\delta_{h,n} \rightarrow 0$, as h decreases and n increases, then the final approximation does not exhibit the Gibbs phenomenon:

Figure 24: The final corrected approximation errors, at $z = 0.5$.

Proposition 4.3. *Along mesh lines in the direction of the three axes, the jumps in the error of the final approximation across the singularity surface or across the boundary are bounded by $C\delta_{h,n}$.*

Proof. Recalling the analysis in Proposition 2.6 for the jumps in the error in the 1D case, we note that all we assume is that there is a bound on the r th order difference and an approximation method that reproduces polynomials of degree $\geq k$. Since here the signature σ_r is defined by the sum of r th order differences in the direction of the three axes, the maximal r th order difference in any direction is bounded by $\delta_{h,n}$, and the result stated follows. \square

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